

Germany's carbon debt, and how it can be managed down with carbon dioxide removal deployment

Carbon dioxide removal (CDR) is a vital precondition to achieving the Paris Agreement's temperature goal. No 1.5°C pathway exists without the deployment of scaled CDR. This raises important questions about the "fair" allocation of CDR deployment by countries. In this brief, we outline Germany's fair allocation based on distributive justice principles.

Main takeaways:

- Germany emitted above 16 Gt CO₂ over an equal per capita basis between 1990 and 2023. Going forward, it plans to emit a further 2.3 Gt CO₂ until its neutrality goal in 2045. This is Germany's historical, and projected future "carbon debt", respectively.
- However, Germany's "fair" CDR contribution is much larger, due to its responsibilities as a historical emitter, and its capability to do more to remove carbon – reflecting the principles of the Paris Agreement.
- We calculate that Germany should deploy 6.4 Gt CO₂ of CDR up to 2045 to align with the Paris Agreement objectives. This is 5.6 Gt CO₂ more than its current plans for 0.8 Gt CO₂.
- To minimise its future carbon debt, and therefore future CDR deployment, Germany must also seek to undertake more stringent emissions reduction efforts.

Limiting warming to 1.5°C requires carbon dioxide removal

Climate action is still not on track to limit global warming to 1.5°C above pre-industrial levels. Despite the urgency, global CO₂ emissions in 2023 increased by 1.6% compared to the previous year², and mitigation efforts are falling short. The remaining carbon budget (RCB) for keeping global warming below 1.5°C, with a 50% likelihood, is rapidly shrinking and is estimated to be 200 Gt CO₂ from the beginning of 2024, subject to uncertainties¹.

In the scenarios assessed by the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) Working Group III, all pathways that align with the Paris Agreement's temperature goal (Article 2.1a) and aim for a global peak in greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, followed by rapid reductions to achieve net zero emissions in the second half of the century (Article 4.1) require both strong emissions reductions and CDR deployment³.

Carbon dioxide removal should be done fairly

Most pathways assessed by the IPCC are based on cost-effectiveness assumptions and are not designed to consider intergenerational and international equity issues^{4,5}. However, equity is a principle enshrined in the Paris Agreement, and equity concerns were also raised during the first Global Stocktake⁶.

Equity fundamentally asks important questions about what constitutes a fair contribution to mitigation for different actors. Effort-sharing approaches that include a calculated emission reduction target based on i) the remaining carbon budget and/or ii) historical emissions have resulted in a negative remaining carbon budget for developed countries. Likewise, all effort-sharing approaches lead to more constrained CO₂ emissions allowance for developed countries⁷.

The "carbon debt" approach reflects two equity principles: responsibility and equality (see methods section). We use this approach to determine Germany's fair-share contribution.

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Germany's climate neutrality target

Germany's modelled domestic pathways to climate neutrality⁸, aligned with the Federal Climate Protection Act (in German, KSG), provide a basis to explore fair and quantitative targets for CDR deployment.

Climate neutrality is defined as reaching net zero anthropogenic GHG emissions directly arising from human activities. The KSG, amended in 2021, sets intermediate GHG emissions targets of cutting 65% by 2030 and 88% by 2040 compared to 1990 levels. The Act also sets a target for achieving climate neutrality by 2045—five years ahead of the EU's target—and envisions a transition towards negative emissions after 2050.

Germany's climate target can only be achieved through a rapid and profound transformation of the entire energy system and CDR methods to compensate for hard-to-abate residual emissions^{8,9}.

Fair carbon dioxide removal expectations for Germany

Based on equal cumulative emissions per capita, Germany's

cumulative CO₂ emissions exceed its equitable share by 2.3 Gt CO₂ out to 2045 (see blue part of the middle bar in Figure 1). In practical terms, Germany plans to emit 2.6 times its fair allocation, while the projected volume of CDR between 2024 and 2045 is 0.8 Gt CO₂ (green bars in the middle bar in Figure 1)⁸.

Germany has the fifth highest historical carbon debt, responsible for top 16.5 Gt CO₂ or 4.3% of global cumulative debt between 1990 and 2023 (top blue bar in Figure 1).

Based on our allocation scheme, Germany should deploy 6.4 [interquartile range: 5.5 – 6.9] Gt CO₂ of CDR until neutrality to align with the Paris Agreement objectives (full yellow bar in Figure 1). This is 5.6 Gt CO₂ more than the planned 0.8 Gt CO₂.

Even though Germany has accounted for conventional and novel CDR options in its mission to achieve neutrality, almost all its existing CDR capacity comes from conventional CDR on land (e.g., afforestation, reforestation, and existing forest). However, in the long term, novel CDR technologies (e.g., DACCS, BECCS, and enhanced weat-

hering) will play a critical role in achieving net-negative emissions⁸. At the current pace, the RCB will be depleted before 2030², underscoring the importance of i) **more stringent emissions reduction efforts to minimise future carbon debt** (see blue part of the

middle bar in Figure 1), and ii) **exploring ways for a sustainable scaling up of CDR capacity**, to keep the Paris Agreement's objectives within reach (see yellow bar in Figure 1) (green part of the middle bar in Figure 1).

Methods for calculating Germany's carbon debt

Net zero carbon debt refers to a country's cumulative emissions from historical levels (here: 1990) to net zero (the target year for Germany's climate neutrality is 2045) that exceed an equal per capita emission pathway.

Equal cumulative per capita emission is one effort-sharing approach and combines two concepts of distributive justice or fairness: responsibility and equality¹¹. Responsibility accounts for each country's historical emissions, while equality translates into equal emission rights for each individual based on a shared carbon budget^{12,13}. To calculate net zero carbon debt or credit for a country or region, three components are required: i) historical emissions, ii) 'fair' allocation of the remaining carbon budget, and iii) future emissions to reach net zero (see Equation 1).

For net zero carbon debt:

*the historical carbon debt for region r , t_{1990} and t_{2023} ,
the time period (historical) for the assessment,
 $pop_{r,t}$, the population of region r in timestep t ,
 POP_t , the global population in timestep t ,
 E_t , the global emissions in timestep t ,
 $e_{r,t}$, the actual regional emissions in timestep t ,
the future carbon debt for region r , t_{2024} , $t_{net-zero}$,
the time period (future) for the assessment, and RCB,
the remaining carbon budget to limit global warming to 1.5°C above pre-industrial levels.*

The first step involves determining the "historical carbon debt or credit"—the CO₂ emissions per region that exceed an equal per capita pathway. We started in 1990, the year often cited as when the IPCC began offering science-based climate guidance to policymakers¹⁴. Historical (1990–

2023) CO₂ emissions (excluding the LULUCF sector) are taken from the PRIMAP-hist dataset², while population data is sourced from the World Bank's World Development Indicators¹⁵. For the remaining carbon budget, we use a value of 200 Gt CO₂ from 2024 onwards, based on the latest estimate to keep warming below 1.5°C with a 50% probability¹. Next, we calculate the regional share of remaining carbon budget emissions, assuming future projections align with the middle-of-the-road Shared Socio-Economic Pathway¹⁷ and Germany's domestic emission projections⁸.

Finally, Germany's future CO₂ emissions to reach net zero were taken from the Ariadne project's target scenarios⁸.

To allocate Germany's CDR fair obligation, we considered its regional share of global historical cumulative carbon debt (4.3%) to derive its contribution from the CDR volume needed under policy-relevant temperature goals.

$$\text{net-zero carbon debt}_r = \sum_{t=t_{1990}}^{t_{2023}} \frac{pop_{r,t}}{POP_t} \times E_t - e_{r,t} + \sum_{t=t_{2024}}^{t_{net-zero}} \frac{pop_{r,t}}{POP_t} \times RCB - e_{r,t}$$

About CDR-PoEt (2021 - 2025)

Carbon Dioxide Removals – Policies and Ethics (CDR-PoEt) examines the ethical and equity implications of policy instruments for CDR, based on interdisciplinary research and stakeholder deliberations. The project specifically evaluates the feasibility ('what can we do from an economic, socio-cultural, and institutional perspective?') and the desirability ('what do we want to do?') of CDR policies and methods in their specific contexts, providing a foundation for developing policy recommendations at local, national and international levels.

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